

SENSETA

Title: From Data Science to product: deploying a Data Science project to production as a web API with minimum effort, using Flask and Docker.

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INTRODUCTION:

A Data Science final product can no longer always be as a static Jupyter Notebook (or equivalent). Nowadays a final Data Science product requires constant un-attended interaction, a web API. But the general Data Science skills are not the same ones required to build web applications.

AIM:

To rapidly convert a Data Science project to a product accessible via a web API, in a robust and efficient manner with minimum, effort using modern, industry tested, best practices.

METHODS:

Using Docker as a robust, efficient and replicable deployment environment and Python Flask, a very simple and minimal web micro framework, convert a Data Science project that might have started as an exploratory data analysis Jupyter Notebook to a product in the form of a web API that other components and applications in the organization can interact with.

RESULTS:

Using this methodology the time taken from exploration to deployment of Data Science products has reduced from weeks to hours. And has been successfully applied in industries like Military Intelligence, Banking, Telecommunications and others, in several continents.

CONCLUSIONS:

A Data Science team can now create a complete product from exploration to deployment and no longer requires deep web development skills to achieve that for most of the projects.

KEYWORDS:

Data Science, Docker, Flask, web, API, deployment, Jupyter Notebook, product

BIOGRAPHY:

Sebastián Ramírez is currently dedicated to the design, study, and implementation of algorithms to solve complex data problems (leading a team of developers) in order to generate new actionable data, applying Machine Learning techniques on Big Data systems.

He has been an invited speaker, judge, mentor in many events related to Big Data, Machine Learning, Coding, etc.

He has contributed to (or created) many Open Source projects (over 70).

He is currently the CTO of Senseta, a Big Data Analytics company, dedicated to solving the most complex data problems for institutions and corporations ranging from Military Intelligence to Telcos.